

Ethene hydrogenation on zeolite-supported rhodium clusters. A mechanistic study by density functional and microkinetic modeling

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Abstract

Experiments showed small Rh clusters, supported in zeolites, to be catalytically active in the hydrogenation of ethene. We report a computational study on the transformations of ethene on zeolite-supported Rh₄ clusters, in particular on the influence of the hydrogen loading of the clusters. Our density functional calculations revealed a general trend of decreasing activation energies of the hydrogenation for increasing H coverage of the metal particles. Furthermore, the coordination of the attacking H ligand crucially affects the hydrogenation barriers. At low H coverage, strongly adsorbed, bridge-bonded H ligands are responsible for the calculated higher barriers while lower barriers were calculated for top-coordinated H ligands near the organic reactants. Microkinetic modeling, based on these electronic structure results, suggests that zeolite-supported Rh₄ clusters are active for hydrogenation of ethene regardless the H loading. Ethene, adsorbed in π -coordinated fashion, was determined to be the active species in this reaction. When hydrogen is present in the system, intermediates derived via dehydrogenation of ethene are not expected.

Keywords: zeolite-supported rhodium, ethene, hydrogenation, DFT, microkinetic modeling.

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Introduction

The catalytic hydrogenation of olefins by transition metal (TM) surfaces and nanoparticles has been widely studied, both in experiments and by modeling based on density functional theory (DFT).^[1-6] The coordination mode of a reacting ethene molecule on the metal sites is often considered as a key factor determining how the hydrogenation reaction proceeds. The preference for π - or *di*- σ -coordination of ethene as well as the adsorption energy of the organic molecule on the metal surface have been discussed as descriptors of the catalytic activity.^[7]

π -bonded ethane, usually somewhat higher in energy on TM surfaces than *di*- σ -coordinated ethene, is considered as the active species for the hydrogenation.^[8-10] A recent computational study on various closed-packed single-crystal TM surfaces^[11] showed that the amount of adsorbed hydrogen can influence the coordination mode of ethene and hence the barriers for ethene hydrogenation. Adsorbed hydrogen was suggested to block available metal sites and to induce surface structure deformations. In this way, the presence of co-adsorbed H atoms promotes the active π -coordination of ethene, thus ultimately enhancing the activity of the TM catalyst.^[11] The surface coverage of ethene also plays a role in determining the preferred coordination mode and the reaction mechanism on TM surfaces.^[5]

Small supported TM clusters may behave rather differently than the corresponding metal surfaces. In the present work we examined the influence of the hydrogen loading on various hydrogenation/dehydrogenation reactions of ethene on the example of zeolite-supported Rh₄ clusters. Such small TM clusters were successfully synthesized in the cavities of dealuminated faujasite zeolite when the samples were pretreated with hydrogen.^[12-15] Also mononuclear rhodium complexes were stabilized in the cavities of the zeolite and were found to catalyze selectively the dimerization of ethene to butene.^[13] These experiments also showed that the hydrogenation of ethene is preferred in the presence of small Rh clusters, yielding ethane as the primary product.^[14] In the present work, we refrained from addressing the dimerization of ethene because in a recent DFT study we were able to show that hydrogenation of ethene will be preferred over dimerization in the excess of hydrogen in the system, in particular when hydrogen is adsorbed in atomic fashion on the metal species.^[16]

In a preceding study^[17] we had examined the structure and the stability of intermediates that may appear due to hydrogenation (ethyl), dehydrogenation (ethylidyne, vinyl, vinylidene) or isomerization (ethylidene) of ethene molecules on hydrogenated Rh₃ and Rh₄ clusters, supported on a faujasite-type zeolite framework. From these DFT results, we constructed a thermodynamic model for the hydrogenation of pertinent organic complexes to predict the dominant species for ranges of temperature and hydrogen pressure.

According to this model, the hydrogenation of ethene occurs more likely if Rh₄ clusters are present in the system, whereas on the smaller Rh₃ cluster ethylidyne intermediates are the dominant species for any temperature and hydrogen pressure studied. Therefore, in the present computational work, we focused on hydrogenated zeolite-supported Rh₄ clusters.

We applied DFT calculations to periodic models to calculate the activation energies of various hydrogenation and dehydrogenation steps that may occur during the catalytic hydrogenation of adsorbed ethene. We also explored how pre-adsorbed hydrogen on the metal particle affects these reaction barriers, hence the preferred reaction pathways. Finally, based on the results of the electronic structure calculations, we developed microkinetic models to gain further insight into the possible intermediates at reaction conditions and on the time scale of the various hydrogenation/dehydrogenation transformations of ethene on small supported Rh clusters, using Rh₄ as example.

Results of density functional calculations

The models used for the calculations were gleaned from our preceding study on the energetics of ethene-derived complexes on hydrogen-loaded small Rh clusters, supported on faujasite.^[17] Accordingly, Rh₄ clusters preferentially adsorb in the supercage of faujasite, near three adjacent four-member rings (4R) of the zeolite framework; see Figure S1 of Supporting Information (SI). Therefore, we addressed here only this adsorption site for the Rh clusters.

Three kind of hydrogen loadings, referred to as low, medium and high coverage, were explored, with total numbers $k = 7, 9$ and 13 , respectively, of H atoms in the system. This value k includes the H atoms adsorbed on the metal particle as well as H atoms of the organic species. As all organic species studied are adsorbed on a Rh₄ cluster, anchored on the zeolite framework, we denote these structures simply by labels C₂H _{x} Y, where $x = 3-6$ is the amount of H atoms of the organic moiety. The label Y refers to the amount of pre-adsorbed hydrogen on the metal cluster, with $Y = L, M, \text{ or } H$ for low, medium and high hydrogen coverage, respectively; see Table 1.

For each H coverage, we explored the transformations of ethene starting from a π - or a $di-\sigma$ -bonded species. We did not address reactions that involve vinylidene, C=CH₂, from a dehydrogenation of vinyl, CHCH₂, or a hydrogenation to ethylidyne, CCH₃, as such complexes on Rh₄ are strongly destabilized, in some cases even implying a notable distortion of the Rh cluster.^[17]

Figures 1 to 3 summarize the calculated results for the transformations studied at low, medium and high hydrogen loading; they provide sketches of the complexes involved together with the calculated values of the corresponding reaction and activation free

energies, G_r and G_a , respectively. The labeling of the reactions in Figures 1 to 3 corresponds to that used in Table 1. The same number is used when analogous hydrogenation/dehydrogenation reactions are referred to; the H coverage will be clear from the context where the labels are mentioned. In Tables S1 and S2 of the SI we collected the relative stability of the pertinent intermediates and transition states (TS) as well as their relative stabilities. Figure S2 of the SI shows more detailed sketches of pertinent TS structures for complexes at low hydrogen coverage.

In experiments, it is difficult to maintain a constant amount of adsorbed H atoms on small rhodium clusters. Our previously reported thermodynamic models show the expected H loadings for a selected temperature and hydrogen pressure.^[18] Accordingly, low ($k = 7$) and medium ($k = 9$) H coverages of supported Rh₄ clusters are favored at temperatures above 450 K and hydrogen pressure values below 10 Pa. On the other hand, clusters with high H loading ($k = 13$) were predicted for lower temperature and higher hydrogen pressure values, including the experimental conditions at which the clusters were found to be active for ethene hydrogenation.^[14] In the following, we will discuss how the coordination of the hydrogen ligands will affect the hydrogenation barriers.

Low hydrogen coverage

In the initial state of the first hydrogenation step **R2** on the path starting from the structure π -C₂H₄_L (π path for short), one finds two bridge-coordinated H ligands at Rh-Rh bonds and one terminal (top) H ligand, adsorbed on a Rh center. The latter H center moves towards one of the CH₂ fragments to form the product, the pseudo ethyl structure, previously described.^[17] The activation free energy for reaction **R2** is calculated at $G_a(\mathbf{R2}) = 18 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ only (Figure 1). In the subsequent hydrogenation step **R3**, a bridge-coordinated H atom is added to the CH₂ moiety of the pseudo ethyl intermediate to form the product ethane, π -C₂H₆_L, with $G_a(\mathbf{R3}) = 68 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. For the two analogous hydrogenation steps starting from *di*- σ ethene, the calculated barriers are almost twice as high: $G_a(\mathbf{R4}) = 41 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $G_a(\mathbf{R5}) = 113 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ (Figure 1). On the *di*- σ path the two subsequent hydrogenation steps involve H ligands initially bridge-coordinated on Rh₄. Along the *di*- σ path, a regular ethyl intermediate, σ -C₂H₅_L, is formed, with only one Rh-C bond via the CH₂ group. That intermediate is by 24 kJ mol⁻¹ less stable than the analogous structure along the π -path, pseudo ethyl π -C₂H₅_L.

Comparing the two subsequent hydrogenation steps **R2** and **R3** on the π -path (Figure 1), it becomes evident that also the coordination of the attacking H ligand can play a crucial role in the hydrogenation reactions. In reaction **R2**, the attacking H ligand is top-coordinated on the metal cluster while in reaction **R3** the H ligand attacking the ethyl moiety is bridge

coordinated. The activation energy $G_a(\mathbf{R2})$ is calculated by 50 kJ mol⁻¹ lower than $G_a(\mathbf{R3}) = 68$ kJ mol⁻¹.

The isomerization between the two complexes with different ethene coordination was calculated to start from the *di*- σ species (Figure 1). In this slightly endergonic step, $G_r(\mathbf{R1}) = 17$ kJ mol⁻¹, the system encounters a rather low barrier, $G_a(\mathbf{R1}) = 30$ kJ mol⁻¹. The resulting π -ethene complex is by 29 kJ mol⁻¹ less stable than the most stable π -ethene configuration where the H ligands are differently positioned on the Rh₄ cluster.

In the dehydrogenation **R6** of the complex *di*- σ -C₂H₄_L, the leaving H atom binds in terminal (*t*) fashion to the same Rh center as the resulting CH group, forming the vinyl complex *t*-CH₂CH_L. This endergonic reaction, $G_r(\mathbf{R6}) = 48$ kJ mol⁻¹, exhibits a notable barrier, $G_r(\mathbf{R6}) = 65$ kJ mol⁻¹. The resulting complex *t*-CH₂CH_L is somewhat unstable (Table S1 of the SI), but the subsequent H migration **R10** of the top H atom to a bridge position (Figure S3 of the SI) offers a facile stabilization to the resulting bridge-bonded (*b*) vinyl complex *b*-CH₂CH_L, with $G_r(\mathbf{R10}) = -37$ kJ mol⁻¹, $G_a(\mathbf{R10}) = 9$ kJ mol⁻¹. The hydrogenation **R8** of the CH₂ moiety to form ethylidene, *b*-CH₃CH_L, is slightly endergonic, $G_r(\mathbf{R8}) = 21$ kJ mol⁻¹, with a moderate barrier, $G_a(\mathbf{R8}) = 35$ kJ mol⁻¹ (Figure 1). The dehydrogenation **R9** of this ethylidene complex to form adsorbed ethylidyne, CH₃C_L, is essentially thermoneutral, $G_r(\mathbf{R9}) = -4$ kJ mol⁻¹, but requires overcoming a notable barrier, $G_a(\mathbf{R9}) = 72$ kJ mol⁻¹.

The ethylidene intermediate *b*-CH₃CH_L may alternatively be formed by the dehydrogenation **R7** of the ethyl moiety σ -C₂H₅_L, Figure 1. In **R7**, a C-H bond of the CH₂ moiety is broken and the leaving H atom coordinates at a terminal position to the Rh₄ cluster, forming the structure *t*-CH₃CH_L, via $G_a(\mathbf{R7}) = 62$ kJ mol⁻¹. Similar to the case of vinyl *t*-CH₂CH_L, the terminal H ligand of the ethylidene complex *t*-CH₃CH_L migrates rather easily, $G_a(\mathbf{R11}) = 30$ kJ mol⁻¹, forming the more stable bridge-bonded complex *b*-CH₃CH_L, $G_r(\mathbf{R11}) = -21$ kJ mol⁻¹ (Figure S3 of the SI).

Medium hydrogen coverage

Analogous reactions, starting from the ethene complexes π or *di*- σ CH₂CH₂_M, were studied for essentially the same series of complexes, but at medium H coverage on the Rh₄ cluster and with a total number $k = 9$ of H atoms in the system. The calculated reaction free energies and relative activation free energies of the various transformation steps are presented in Figure 2.

Consistently, reaction **R2** is the hydrogenation of π -bonded ethene, π -CH₂CH₂_M, to ethyl, involving H addition of a top ligand, with the calculated activation free energy $G_a(\mathbf{R2}) = 11$ kJ mol⁻¹. Ethane is formed from ethyl in the second hydrogenation step **R3** and, as for

low H coverage, the attacking H is initially bridge-coordinated to a Rh-Rh bond of the supported cluster. The calculated activation free energy $G_a(\mathbf{R3}) = 73 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, is similar to the value determined for the corresponding reaction at low H coverage. Starting from *di*- σ -bonded ethane, the first hydrogenation **R4** proceeds with activation free energy $G_a(\mathbf{R4}) = 37 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and involves a top-coordinated H ligand (Figure 2). On the σ -path the hydrogenation **R5** to ethane is endergonic, $G_r(\mathbf{R5}) = 22 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, and has a relatively high activation free energy, $G_a(\mathbf{R5}) = 54 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. A detailed analysis of the reaction coordinate for **R5** (Figure 2) on the Rh₄ cluster reveals a two-step process. First, the attacking bridge H atom migrates to a top position close to the organic moiety. This migration is endergonic by 30 kJ mol^{-1} and has activation free energy of 47 kJ mol^{-1} . The subsequent H addition is slightly exergonic, $G_r = -7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, with a moderately low activation free energy. $G_a = 24 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. This step leads to the formation of the product ethane, Figure S4 of the SI. Note that the latter hydrogenation barrier is by 30 kJ mol^{-1} lower than the one calculated for the one-step process **R5** and by 90 kJ mol^{-1} lower than the one calculated for the analogous hydrogenation reaction on the cluster Rh₄_L. Such intermediate structures with H atoms at top position were not found at low H coverage due to the high preference for bridge-coordination of H ligands at the unsaturated Rh cluster. If formed, such intermediates may be assumed to be very short-lived.

The free energy barriers, calculated for the two dehydrogenation steps **R7** from ethyl to ethylidene and **R9** from ethylidene to ethylidyne, are very similar: $G_a(\mathbf{R7}) = 54 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $G_a(\mathbf{R9}) = 49 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ (Figure 2). Rather low barriers were calculated for the dehydrogenation of *di*- σ -ethene to vinyl, $G_a(\mathbf{R6}) = 10 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, and the hydrogenation of vinyl to ethylidene, $G_a(\mathbf{R8}) = 19 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The transformation **R1** of *di*- σ -ethene to π -ethene at medium hydrogen coverage occurs within the two most stable complexes. The change of the coordination mode from *di*- σ , involving two Rh centers, to the π mode, involving only one Rh center, is exergonic, $G_r(\mathbf{R1}) = -43 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, over a moderately low calculated activation free energy barrier, $G_a(\mathbf{R1}) = 28 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

High hydrogen coverage

At the highest hydrogen loading (total number $k = 13$ of H atoms in the system), the supported Rh₄ cluster is already rather saturated with H ligands. Any attempt of adding more hydrogen resulted in significantly elongated Rh-Rh distances ($> 300 \text{ pm}$) and led to a reorientation of the complex against the zeolite framework. Therefore, we refrained from addressing dehydrogenation reactions of the complexes of π - and *di*- σ -bonded ethene. Figure 3 shows the resulting simplified scheme of the reactions studied. Starting from π -CH₂CH₂_H, the hydrogenation reaction **R2** involves an H addition of a top-coordinated

ligand to adsorbed ethane. Not unexpectedly, this transformation has rather low activation free energy barrier, $G_a(\mathbf{R2}) = 10 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The calculated barrier for the analogous hydrogenation reaction **R4**, starting from *di*- σ -ethene, is twice as high, but still relatively low, $G_a(\mathbf{R4}) = 20 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. Nearly equal values were calculated for the second hydrogenation steps **R3** and **R5**, for both types of coordination of the ethyl ligand: $G_a(\mathbf{R3}) = 33 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $G_a(\mathbf{R5}) = 31 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. Reaction **R3** on the π -path is slightly endergonic, $G_r(\mathbf{R3}) = 21 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, while the analogous transformation **R5** is slightly exergonic on the σ -path, $G_r(\mathbf{R5}) = -12 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ (Figure 3).

The transformation **R1** of the *di*- σ -bonded to π -bonded ethene is slightly exergonic, $G_r(\mathbf{R1}) = -14 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, via a moderate barrier, $G_a(\mathbf{R1}) = 35 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. Due to different positions of the H ligands on the Rh₄ cluster at high H loading, the resulting complex is by 34 kJ mol^{-1} less stable than the most stable π -ethene system, $\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-H}$.

Discussion

In Figure 4 we consider the free energy profiles for the hydrogenation of ethene to ethane on the supported Rh₄ cluster. For each of the three hydrogen coverages studied, we compare the energy profiles for both types of coordination of an ethene molecule (π and *di*- σ). The overall hydrogenation reaction of ethene in the gas phase to ethane, also in the gas phase, as occurring on a zeolite-supported Rh₄ cluster is exergonic, regardless of the amount of pre-adsorbed hydrogen. At low H loading, the overall reaction is exergonic by only 17 kJ mol^{-1} . The process is calculated to be thermodynamically much more favorable for medium and high H loading, with free reaction energies of -71 kJ mol^{-1} and -73 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively. The last step on the hydrogenation path is the desorption of the product ethane into the gas phase. At low H coverage, this latter step is endergonic, on average by 32 kJ mol^{-1} , with rather similar free energy changes for π - and *di*- σ -coordinated reactants. Such a similarity for the desorption of π - and *di*- σ -derived ethane also holds for medium H loading; here the final step slightly exergonic, by 11 kJ mol^{-1} on average. At high H loading, the desorption of ethane derived via the π -path is endergonic by 12 kJ mol^{-1} , but it is exergonic, by 5 kJ mol^{-1} , for the desorption of *di*- σ -derived ethane. In summary, at 300 K, releasing the product ethane from the zeolite-supported Rh₄ cluster into the gas phase product will not demand a significant amount of energy.

π -bonded adsorbed ethene is thermodynamically more stable than the analogous *di*- σ -bonded complex, regardless of the hydrogen coverage (Figure 4). With increasing hydrogen loading of the cluster, the metal centers are becoming more saturated and the *di*- σ -ethene complex becomes increasingly destabilized with respect to the π -bonded coordination, as already reported in our previous study.^[17] The free energy difference

increases from 13 kJ mol⁻¹, to 43 kJ mol⁻¹ and 48 kJ mol⁻¹ for low, medium and high hydrogen coverage, respectively. Furthermore, the calculated free energy barriers for the first hydrogenation step **R4** of ethene to ethyl on the *di-σ*-path are almost twice as large as the corresponding barriers (**R2**) on the *π*-path, again for all hydrogen loadings studied. These results agree with those of previous theoretical^[8, 10] and experimental^[9, 19-20] studies that suggested the *π*-bonded ethene as the active species for the hydrogenation to ethane. A recent paper on the hydrogenation of ethene on TM surfaces^[11] also determined the hydrogenation of *π*-bonded ethene to be favored, reporting even lower activation energies in the presence of co-adsorbed hydrogen. The present results for small hydrogenated Rh₄ clusters are in agreement with this work on TM surfaces. In the presence of co-adsorbed H on the cluster Rh₄, the more active *π*-bonding of ethene is favored due to saturation of the metal centers, thus promoting hydrogenation. In general, with increasing H coverage of the metal moiety, the free energy barriers of the hydrogenation decrease, irrespective of the coordination mode (*π* or *di-σ*) of the ethene molecule (Figure 4).

Aleksandrov et al.^[6] examined computationally the hydrogenation of ethyl to ethane on TM surfaces and nanoparticles. Accordingly, the barriers for hydrogenation decrease with the adsorption energy of the surface H atoms involved in the reaction. The need of weakly bound hydrogen on the surface of a catalyst was also shown experimentally.^[7] Our present results for the hydrogenation of ethane on TM particles agree with those findings. At low hydrogen coverage, the strong interaction between the attacking bridge-adsorbed H atoms and the Rh centers may be the reason for the calculated relatively high free energies of activation for the hydrogenation of ethyl to ethane: 70 kJ mol⁻¹ for the *π*-path and 114 kJ mol⁻¹ for the *di-σ*-path, Figure 4. Higher adsorption energies were calculated for bridge coordinated ligands on small zeolite-supported Rh clusters compared to top coordinated ligands.^[18] In most cases a hydrogenation involving bridge H ligands proceeds via an initial migration of the hydrogen to a top position; on a Rh₄ cluster with medium H loading the corresponding barrier is 42 kJ mol⁻¹ (Figure S4 of the SI). Therefore, the higher activation energies determined at low H coverage may be caused by the lack of top-coordinated H adsorbates in close vicinity of the organic species, requiring a preceding H migration step. With increasing hydrogen loading, the interaction between the H ligands and the metal particle is weakened, H ligands occupy top positions, and the barriers decrease.

Results of microkinetic modeling and discussion

To gain insight into the time evolution of the systems, as implied by the results of these electronic structure calculations, we constructed several microkinetic models, representing various scenarios for the three H coverages just discussed. Accordingly, the reaction network used for high H loading did not comprise dehydrogenation reactions. In all cases, the number of H atoms in the system was assumed to be constant, in agreement with the DFT models; this assumption limits the general validity of these models. As two H ligands are consumed in the hydrogenation of ethene to the product ethane, formally another hydrogen molecule has to be adsorbed, to keep the H loading of the cluster unchanged. Therefore, all scenarios imply that, once the product desorbs, dissociative H₂ adsorption occurs as a very fast step, to regenerate the initial state of the system in a quasi-instantaneous fashion. As we shall see later on, this assumption seems acceptable as available adsorption sites are typically filled within about 10⁻⁷ sec. Similarly short adsorption times were predicted by kinetic Monte Carlo (KMC) simulations for the adsorption of CO on Au₆ clusters.^[21] To probe and justify the assumption of a quasi-instantaneous replenishing of the hydrogen content, we also examined a microkinetic model with an explicit hydrogen adsorption step. Yet, we did not detect any significant effect on the results as shown in Section S5 of the SI; see especially Figure S5. For simplicity, we also excluded in our scenarios any additional hydrogen adsorption, possibly blocking the adsorption of ethene. Further technical details of the microkinetic models are discussed in the Section “Computational details” and the SI.

The model system studied herein represents small rhodium clusters in the cavities of faujasite, which, as described in the Introduction, have been successfully synthesized by Serna et al.^[13-14]. These species were stabilized by pretreatment of the catalyst with hydrogen and were active for the catalytic hydrogenation of ethene to ethane at 303 K and 10 kPa ethene partial pressure. Taking into account the experimental conditions we estimated the ratio $R = [\square\text{-Rh}] : [\text{C}_2\text{H}_4]$ of initially available catalytic sites (Rh clusters) and reactant molecules to be close to 1; for details, see the SI. Therefore, we carried out kinetic simulations at 300 K, an ethene partial pressure of 10 kPa, and an initial ratio $R = 1$. We address the species available in an ensembles of structures via mole fractions, χ , with respect to the initially available number of reactant molecules, ethene. Hence, the mole fractions of all species involved, including those one in the gas phase, are normalized to 1.

Batch-type simulations

In the following, we will discuss results of batch-type microkinetic simulations where a given amount of ethene in the gas phase is used as input to the hydrogenated Rh clusters, i.e., with the corresponding initial mole fraction of 1. Figures 5a and 5b show the time evolution of the mole fractions of the various species on a logarithmic time scale at medium and high hydrogen loading, respectively. The system reaches a stationary (final) state, once all of the ethene initially provided is hydrogenated to the product ethane.

As the lowest hydrogen coverage is very unlikely to exist in the experimental conditions herein we refrain from discussing it in detail; more information is given in section S5 and Figure S5 of the SI.

At medium H loading (Figure 5a) one may discriminate three subsequent stages at different time scales. In Stage 1, the initial adsorption of ethene from the gas phase, to both coordination modes, reaction steps **A1** (π -path) and **A2** (di - σ path), is completed quite fast, after about 10^{-7} s, forming the complexes π -C₂H₄_M and di - σ -C₂H₄_M (Table 1). Subsequently, di - σ -bound ethene is quickly converted, via reaction **R1**, to the more stable π -bound ethene species. In Stage 2, the first hydrogenation step proceeds on a substantially longer time scale. In consequence, the mole fractions of π -adsorbed ethene and ethyl species reach their maximum value (Table 2) and remain approximately constant, $\chi(\pi$ -C₂H₄_M) = 0.9 and $\chi(\pi$ -C₂H₅_M) = 0.1 (Figure 5a). This steady-state situation persists from about 10^{-7} s until some 10^{-1} s. In Stage 3, the hydrogenation of the adsorbed ethyl species takes place, to form the product ethane. Thus, for medium H loading, ethane forms via the π -path, steps **R3** and **D1** (Table 1).

At high H loading (Figure 5b), the three stages are still evident, but they are predicted to occur at shorter timescales. Also, the three stages overlap to some extent. Recall that in this case the reaction network is much simpler (Figure 3) than at medium H loading just discussed (Figure 2). The adsorption of the gas phase ethene in Stage 1 is completed somewhat faster, essentially after some 10^{-7} s. In parallel the two types of ethyl species are formed via reactions **R2** and **R4** starting at about 10^{-10} s (Table 1). The hydrogenation of the ethene species, π - and di - σ -C₂H₄_H, is very fast in consequence of the calculated very low relative activation energy, $G_a(\mathbf{R2}) = 10$ kJ mol⁻¹ and $G_a(\mathbf{R4}) = 20$ kJ mol⁻¹, respectively (Figure 2). The formation of di - σ -C₂H₄_H, reaction **R1**, occurs at a longer time scale, in about 10^{-7} s. This late occurrence of **R1** leads to the formation of a minor amount of σ -C₂H₅_H species via step **R4**, Figure 5b. Hence, a small amount of the product in the gas phase is produced via the σ -path (Table 2), from about 10^{-7} s. After the intermediates on the σ -path, σ -C₂H₄_H and σ -C₂H₅_H, are fully consumed, either via the hydrogenation reactions **R4** and **R5** or the conversion **R1**, the π -path becomes dominant from about 10^{-7} s. For high

H coverage, the steady-state situation in Stage 2 persists only from 10^{-7} s until some 10^{-5} s (Figure 5b). At high H loading, such a shorter time span is consistent with the lower calculated barrier for the second hydrogenation step **R3** which appears to be the rate-limiting step for producing ethane. At high H loading, ethane is already formed during Stage 2 (Figure 5b).

The time required for completing the overall reaction decreases with increasing H loading, from 4×10^1 s at medium H loading to 6×10^{-3} s at high H loading. If one quantifies the start of Stage 3 as the time required for accumulating 50% of the overall amount of ethane in the gas phase, then the beginning of this final stage decreases from 5.6 s at medium H coverage to 6×10^{-4} s at high H coverage (Figures 5a, 5b). We also carried out simulations at 500 K and, as expected, at this higher temperature, the time for accumulating 50% of the overall amount of ethane decreased by 5–7 orders of magnitude at all H loadings studied; see Figure S6 of the SI.

For further analysis of the catalytic system studied, we also explored simulations with a reduced amount of the initially available free Rh sites with respect to the overall amount of ethene in the system, $R = 0.2$ (Figure 5c). In this case, the system proceeds through 5 turnovers before the full amount of ethene from the gas phase is converted to ethane. We focus the following **discussion** to high H loading; see Table 2.

During Stage 1 of these simulations, when ethene is adsorbed to form π - and $di\text{-}\sigma$ - $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-H}$ via **A1** and **A2**, respectively, two inflection points are visible in the time evolution of its mole fraction (Figure 5c), related to the formation of a small amount of ethane, directly from $di\text{-}\sigma$ species. This intermediate process finishes after all $di\text{-}\sigma$ species are consumed via reactions **R4** and **R5** or transformed to π -bonded species via reaction **R1**. The steady-state situation of Stage 2 continues longer than for $R = 1$, until 4×10^{-3} s. The mole fractions of key intermediates reach their maximum values: $\chi(\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-H}) = 0.15$, corresponding to 74% of the available Rh sites, and $\chi(\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{-H}) = 0.05$ (Table 2).

Furthermore, the formation of ethane is significantly slowed down. The level of 50 % ethane accumulated in the gas phase is reached after 2×10^{-3} s (Figure 5c), essentially one order of magnitude slower than in the analogous model with $R = 1$ (Figure 5b). Immediately after all available ethene in the gas phase is consumed, the adsorbates π -ethene and π -ethyl are converted to ethane via reactions **R2** and **R3**. The initial amount of free sites is simultaneously recovered and the system acquires its final state after 8×10^{-3} s (Figure 5c).

Extrapolating from a situation where the initially available free catalyst sites are far fewer than the initial number of ethene molecules in the gas phase, one may reach the behaviour of a system in a formally constant flow of ethene (Figure S7 of the SI). Such a

continuous-flow scenario allows one to determine easily the net rate of the product formation as the linear increase in time of the accumulated amount of ethane in the gas phase. The resulting net rates of the ethane production for the three different H loadings are presented in Table 3. In general the calculated net rate of ethane production increases with hydrogen loading, from $6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, to $1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and $1 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for low, medium, and high H loading, respectively, at a temperature $T = 300 \text{ K}$. As anticipated, similarly enhanced rates are also determined by raising the temperature (Table 3). At the elevated temperature $T = 500 \text{ K}$, rates are enhanced by typically 5 to 6 orders of magnitude.

In summary, π -bonded species have been determined to dominate the adsorbed intermediates at the metal clusters, demonstrating that these species are active during the hydrogenation. Although dehydrogenation reactions were included in the reaction network at low and medium H loading, no notable fractions of dehydrogenation products were predicted by the kinetic modeling.

Sensitivity analysis

We carried out a sensitivity analysis of microkinetic models at 300 K and the three H loadings studied with a reduced amount of free Rh sites, $R = 0.2$, and constant-flow conditions. Here, we will address only the results for the high H loading because the trends, determined for low and medium H loading, are rather similar (Figure S8 of the SI). Figure 6 shows the resulting normalized sensitivity coefficients *NSC* (see “Computational details”) of the net rate of ethane production. The hydrogenation reactions of ethene (**R2**) and ethyl (**R3**) species on the π -path were determined to be the most crucial elementary steps for the production of ethane in the gas phase. A high *NSC* value was calculated also for the final step in the reaction network, namely the desorption (**D1**) of the product from the $\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_6\text{-H}$ complex. The rate of ethane production depends to a much smaller degree on other elementary reaction steps. The sensitivity analysis corroborates the importance of the π -adsorption mode of ethene for the hydrogenation reaction.

Conclusions

We reported a DFT study of the transformations of ethene that may occur at the conditions of catalytic hydrogenation over zeolite-supported Rh_4 clusters. Invoking models with periodic boundary conditions, we examined three hydrogen coverages of the metal clusters. The calculated barriers for hydrogenation decrease with increasing hydrogen loading of the clusters. At low H loading where the metal centers are only partially saturated, H ligands bind preferably in bridge fashion to the metal species. This stronger adsorption of the H atoms involved in the hydrogenation processes leads to higher activation free energies. With

increasing H loading, top coordination becomes favorable. In this way the hydrogen loading not only promotes π -bonding of the ethene moiety, but also provides more weakly bound top-coordinated H ligands as more active species; hence lower barriers are calculated in such a situation.

Our DFT calculations also suggest that H addition reactions, which include bridge bonded ligands, proceed in a stepwise fashion. Initially, the hydrogen atom migrates to a top site close to the organic species, before the actual hydrogenation occurs. Such migration (diffusion) of the attacking H occurs easily on TM surfaces,^[22] whereas on small metal clusters, as examined here, it may proceed via moderate barriers.

Microkinetic modeling predicts that at 300 K ethane formation is feasible at all hydrogen loadings of Rh₄ clusters studied. The activity of the catalytic system is enhanced, i.e., the net rate of ethane production is higher, when more hydrogen is pre-adsorbed on the metal moiety. The calculated mole fractions of intermediates at steady-state, at conditions formally equivalent to a continuous-flow scenario, and a sensitivity analysis showed that π -bonded ethene is the active species in the hydrogenation reaction on small zeolite-supported Rh clusters.

Computational details

All electronic structure calculations were carried out on periodic supercell models using DFT methods as implemented in the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP).^[23-26] We applied an exchange-correlation functional in the form of the generalized gradient approximation, specifically the functional suggested by Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof (PBE).^[27-28] The intermediate structures were optimized as in our preceding work.^[17]

We did not examine intermediates on bare Rh₄ clusters because preceding studies had shown^[18, 29-30] that (reverse) spillover of H atoms from bridging hydroxyl groups of the zeolite to Rh clusters is energetically favorable. Most complexes of the initial and final states of the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation reactions were taken from our earlier work.^[17] In some cases we derived the structures directly from the transition states to ensure the same coordination of the H ligands as in the initial state.

The reaction pathways of the various transformations were approximated using the nudged elastic band (NEB) approach.^[31] The structures of the beads with the highest energy obtained in the NEB calculations were refined by applying the dimer method.^[32] All obtained transition state structures were confirmed as first-order saddle points of the potential energy surface by a partial normal mode analysis at the harmonic level. When analyzing the vibrational modes, we included the organic adsorbate, the supported hydrogenated Rh₄ cluster, as well as the atoms of the three four-member rings that formed

the adsorption site in the zeolite framework. A similar vibrational analysis was carried out to confirm that the geometry optimization of the new structures used for initial and final states of the reactions resulted in local minimum structures.

All energy values reported herein represent relative Gibbs free energy at 300 K and 101325 Pa pressure; they were calculated in standard fashion for systems formally in the gas phase, using statistical thermodynamics.^[33] Hence, a process with a positive change of the Gibbs free energy is endergonic. The entropy values of the supported Rh₄ clusters and the adsorbates (hydrogen atoms, organic moiety) were calculated in the harmonic approximation. The ideal-gas approximation, including rotational and translation contributions to the entropy term, was used for deriving the Gibbs free energy of molecules in the gas phase.

The elementary steps describing the transformations used for modeling the low H coverage are shown in Table 1. All “surface” reactions on the Rh₄ cluster, labelled **R1** to **R11**, were modeled using transition state theory.^[34] They include hydrogenation reactions for both coordination modes of ethene (π , *di- σ*), dehydrogenation reactions, and various other transformations between the two binding modes of ethene as well as species with different coordination of the H ligands (*t*- and *b*-CHCH₂, *t*- and *b*-CHCH₃). No dehydrogenation reactions were modeled in the case of high hydrogen loading in view of the saturation of all metal sites of the cluster Rh₄. Therefore, the model addressing high H loading includes only the reactions **R1** to **R5**.

The adsorption processes of ethene and hydrogen from the gas phase were assumed to be a non-activated and reversible. We applied collision theory for the adsorption of π - or *di- σ* -bonded ethene, reactions **A1** and **A2**.^[35] We assumed the desorption of the product ethane from the cluster to be irreversible, i.e., reactions **D1** and **D2** for π - or *di- σ* -derived species. These latter processes were assigned activation energies equal to the adsorption energies of the corresponding species.^[35] This assumption seems adequate as our calculations showed that the desorption of the product is strongly facilitated by the concurrent adsorption of a new ethene molecule. The concerted replacement of ethane by ethene is calculated exothermic by at least 178 kJ mol⁻¹. Under experimental conditions of a constant gas flow of ethene (as used in the experiments^[13-14]), re-adsorption of the product is unlikely. For easy checking, we summarized all assumptions invoked in the microkinetic models in Table S3 of the SI.

After describing all elementary steps, their rates were calculated and the resulting system of ordinary differential equations was integrated using the BzzMath library.^[36] The resulting probability densities for ensembles of Rh₄ clusters with various organic adsorbates

are addressed here as mole fractions of the total amount of the initially supplied reactant molecules. A detailed description of the parameters used in the microkinetic models is provided in Section S5 of the SI.

Invoking a sensitivity analysis,^[37] the reaction steps within a network may be identified that are controlling the formation of the product. For this purpose, the kinetic parameters (in our case the rate constants k_i) were perturbed one-at-a-time. Hence, for each reaction of a reaction network, a simulation with the perturbed parameter set is to be carried out to quantify the change of the output quantities X_k . In the present study, a sensitivity analysis was carried out for the simulations with a reduced initial amount of available free sites, $R = 0.2$, employing the calculated net rate of the ethane production as single output quantity. In passing, we note that this situation may be taken to yield a rough approximation of continuous-flow conditions, cf. Figures 5c and S7c of the SI. The normalized sensitivity coefficients NSC_i of the rate constants k_i were then calculated as follows, using $\Delta k_i/k_i = 0.1$:^[37]

$$NSC_i = d \ln X / d \ln k_i \approx (k_i / \Delta k_i) (\Delta X / X) = [k_{i,0} / (k_i - k_{i,0})] [(X_i - X_0) / X_0]$$

The resulting values NSC_i provide a quantitative measure of the sensitivity of the overall production rate. A larger positive or negative value of a coefficient NSC_i indicates a stronger positive or negative influence, respectively, of reaction i on the formation rate of the product.

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Table 1. Elementary reaction steps in the microkinetic models including the transformation reactions (**R**) of ethene-derived intermediates as well as the adsorption (**A**) of species from the gas phase on a faujasite-supported cluster Rh₄ and the analogous desorption (**D**) into the gas phase. The labels Rh₄_Y refer to models with 3, 5 or 9 H ligands adsorbed, at low, medium, and high H loading, Y = L, M, and H, respectively.

Label	Elementary reaction step
A1	$C_2H_4(g) + Rh_4_Y \leftrightarrow \pi-C_2H_4_Y$
A2	$C_2H_4(g) + Rh_4_Y \leftrightarrow \sigma-C_2H_4_Y$
R1	$\pi-C_2H_4_Y \leftrightarrow \sigma-C_2H_4_Y$
R2	$\pi-C_2H_4_Y \leftrightarrow \pi-C_2H_5_Y$
R3	$\pi-C_2H_5_Y \leftrightarrow \pi-C_2H_6_Y$
R4	$\sigma-C_2H_4_Y \leftrightarrow \sigma-C_2H_5_Y$
R5	$\sigma-C_2H_5_Y \leftrightarrow \sigma-C_2H_6_Y$
R6^a	$\sigma-C_2H_4_Y \leftrightarrow CHCH_2_Y$
R7^a	$\sigma-C_2H_5_Y \leftrightarrow CHCH_3_Y$
R8^a	$CHCH_2_Y \leftrightarrow CHCH_3_Y$
R9^a	$CHCH_3_Y \leftrightarrow CCH_3_Y$
R10^b	$t-CHCH_2_Y \leftrightarrow b-CHCH_2_Y$
R11^b	$t-CHCH_3_Y \leftrightarrow b-CHCH_3_Y$
D1	$\pi-C_2H_6_Y \leftrightarrow C_2H_6(g) + Rh_4_Y$
D2	$\sigma-C_2H_6_Y \leftrightarrow C_2H_6(g) + Rh_4_Y$

^a Not considered for high H loading, Y = H. ^b Interconversion of species with H adsorbed at top (*t*) and bridge (*b*) sites only considered at low hydrogen loading, Y = L.

Table 2. Largest values of the mole fractions, χ , of species obtained from microkinetic simulations for the three H loadings studied ($Y = L, M$, and H) at various initial conditions: initial ratio $R = [\square\text{-Rh}] : [\text{C}_2\text{H}_4]$, and temperature T . Only species with $\chi > 10^{-2}$ are listed.

Y		Initial conditions		
		$R = 1, T = 300 \text{ K}$	$R = 0.2, T = 300 \text{ K}$	$R = 1, T = 500 \text{ K}$
L	$\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4_L$	0.99 ^a	0.20 ^a	0.96
	$\sigma\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4_L$	0.32	0.08	0.02
	$\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5_L$			0.02
M	$\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4_M$	0.90 ^a	0.18 ^a	0.74
	$\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5_M$	0.10 ^a	0.02 ^a	0.22
	$\sigma\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4_M$	0.14	0.04	0.01
	$\sigma\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5_M$			0.05
H	$\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4_H$	0.58 ^a	0.15 ^a	0.01
	$\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5_H$	0.21 ^a	0.05 ^a	0.06
	$\sigma\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4_H$	0.36	0.08	0.04
	$\sigma\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5_H$	0.05	0.01	
	$\sigma\text{-C}_2\text{H}_6_H$	0.02		

^a Occurring during the approximate steady-state (Stage 2, see text). Such quasi steady-state conditions are not calculated for higher temperatures; see Figure S6 of the SI.

Table 3. Calculated net rates^a (s^{-1}) for accumulating gas phase product ethane obtained from the microkinetic modeling at constant-flow-type conditions for the three H loadings studied: $Y = L, M$, and H .

$T, \text{ K}$	300	500
L	6.3×10^{-3}	1.8×10^4
M	1.3×10^{-1}	9.0×10^4
H	1.0×10^3	1.0×10^8

^a Rates scaled by $1/R$ to keep values from simulations with different amounts of active sites comparable.

Figure 1. Scheme of hydrogenation and dehydrogenation reactions of ethene on a zeolite-supported Rh_4 cluster, explored at *low* hydrogen coverage, $k = 7$; see also Table 1. The zeolite with one Al center per unit cell and one additional adsorbed H ligand, not participating in the various transformations, are omitted for clarity, except for the complexes $t\text{-CHCH}_3\text{-L}$, $b\text{-CHCH}_3\text{-L}$, and $\text{CCH}_3\text{-L}$, for which all H ligands are shown. For each transformation, the calculated reaction free energies (values in black) and the corresponding relative activation free energies (values in red) are given in kJ mol^{-1} . The structure of $\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-L}$ resulting from reaction **R1** differs from the most stable π -complex of ethene at low hydrogen coverage.

Figure 2. Scheme of hydrogenation and dehydrogenation reactions of ethene on a zeolite-supported Rh_4 cluster, explored for *medium* hydrogen coverage, $k = 9$. Layout as in Figure 1. The zeolite with one Al center per unit cell and three additional H ligands, not participating in the various transformations, are omitted for clarity, except for the complexes CHCH_3_M and CCH_3_M , where two such H ligands are not shown.

Figure 3. Simplified scheme of the hydrogenation and isomerization reactions of ethene on a zeolite-supported Rh_4 cluster, at *high* hydrogen coverage, $k = 13$. In view of the complexity of the structures at *high* H coverage, the orientation of the ligands is omitted for clarity. The structure of $\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4_H$ resulting from reaction **R1** differs from the most stable π -complex of ethene at high hydrogen coverage.

Figure 4. Energy profiles of the hydrogenation of π -bonded (black lines) and *di*- σ -bonded (green lines) ethene to ethane on a zeolite-supported Rh₄ cluster at low, medium and high hydrogen loading (top to bottom). The relative free energies of the reactions (black values) and the corresponding activation free energies (red values) are given in kJ mol⁻¹. IS(g) and FS(g) refer to the initial and the final states of the reactions, where the zeolite-supported Rh₄ cluster carries the appropriate number of H ligands and ethene or ethane are in the gas phase.

Figure 5. Mole fractions, χ , of species from batch-type microkinetic simulations with the initial ratio $R = [\square\text{-Rh}] : [\text{C}_2\text{H}_4]$, i.e., equal amounts of free Rh sites and ethene molecules, for a) medium and b) high H loading at 300 K. Panel c) shows the evolution of the mole fractions with time for a simulation at high H loading and a reduced amount of initially available Rh sites, $R = 0.2$. Color coding of pertinent species: (1) red – $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{g})$; (2) blue – $\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-Y}$; (3) yellow – $\sigma\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-Y}$; (4) purple – $\pi\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{-Y}$; (5) cyan – $\sigma\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5\text{-Y}$; (6) green – $\text{C}_2\text{H}_6(\text{g})$; (7) black dashed – available free sites $\text{Rh}_4\text{-Y}$.

Figure 6. Normalized sensitivity coefficients NSC_i for the batch-type microkinetic model with high hydrogen loading (see Figure 3), estimated using data from simulations with a reduced amount of free Rh sites at 300 K; see text for details.